

Stochastic Dynamics Monte Carlo Simulation for prompt supercritical systems

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ABSTRACT

Abstract: Most Pressurized Water Reactors in China rely on external neutron sources for start-up, except for Russian-designed reactors. Because neutron sources are expensive and unstable, techniques of reactor start-up without external sources have become an important research focus. During the initial phase of start-up, the stochastic neutron transport equation is used instead of the Boltzmann transport equation. It describes neutron fluctuations in the early development of the neutron field. Accurate simulation of core physics during start-up is essential for safe reactor operation. This study develops a three-dimensional continuous-energy solver for the stochastic neutron transport equation. The solver is implemented in the Monte Carlo code NECP-MCX. Calculations on benchmarks, including bare plutonium spheres and CALIBAN, achieved accuracy comparable to other codes and experiments. The proposed approach can be applied to analyze neutron behavior during reactor start-up.

Keywords: stochastic neutron transport equation; Monte Carlo; burst waiting-time; NECP-MCX

1. INTRODUCTION

External neutron sources are being gradually phased out in commercial PWRs due to cost and radiation concerns. During later fuel cycles, start-up often proceeds without external sources. However, mature industrial practice for first-cycle (C1) start-up remains limited, except for VVER reactors. Using only the intrinsic radioactivity of nuclear fuel introduces some challenges, including detector blind zones and strong neutron-field fluctuations at near-zero power. Williams summarized the stochastic neutron transport equation (SNTE) [1], and applied it to nuclear systems to explain neutron fluctuations under weak-source and zero-power conditions.

1.1. Stochastic Processes in Reactors

Stochastic processes in reactors arise from the randomness of fission events and neutron emission [2]. Stochastic behavior in reactors was first recognized in weak-source start-up experiments on the GODIVA fast burst reactor at Los Alamos National Laboratory (LANL). The burst waiting-time (BWT) exhibited pronounced stochasticity rather than determinism [3]. This result indicates strong temporal fluctuations in the neutron population. These effects are most evident in weak neutron fields. In strong fields, statistical regularity is typically described by the Boltzmann equation. In weak-source start-up, fluctuations of neutron population affect safety. The probability of unsafe start-up is the probability that neutron population remains below a prescribed threshold [4]. A higher neutron population in deeply subcritical conditions improves detector observability and therefore safety.

1.2. Development of the SNTE Methods

Stochastic dynamics methods have been studied for decades. In recent years, increased computing power has renewed interest in solving the SNTE.

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1.2.1. Development of Theoretical Research

Stochastic dynamics theory evolved alongside ignition studies of fast burst reactors. Hansen first investigated the topic [5]. He defined weak neutron sources using source intensity, neutron lifetime, fission multiplicity, and the David factor to explain BWT distributions. Pál first formulated SNTE in phase space by applying probability conservation to the probability density function (PDF) of neutron population [6]. Bell generalized the derivation to space–energy form and incorporated delayed precursors, sources, and solution simplifications [7]. Subsequent theories mainly build upon this derivation. It is now known as the Pál-Bell equations. Muñoz-Cobo et al. derived a master equation for the probability generating function to model zero-power detector statistics [8]. Williams et al. linked the PDF of neutron population in weak-source conditions to safety start-up. They computed probabilities of safe start-up under prescribed source and reactivity conditions [4], [9]-[12]. These studies provide guidance for reactor start-up in the presence of detector blind zones.

1.2.2. Development of Numerical Simulation

The Pál-Bell equations are nonlinear adjoint transport equations with source terms. It is more difficult to solve numerically than the Boltzmann equation. Early SN-based solvers include Bell's NDT3 [7] and MacMillan's SSB [13]. Humbert et al. later showed that the BWT of a delayed supercritical reactor follows a gamma distribution. They used the SN code PANDA to compute the BWT and the probability of initiation (POI) for CALIBAN [14]. LANL later extended PARTISN by adding a neutron population PDF module that can compute the POI and the probability of survival (POS) [15], [16]. Xiao et al. implemented SN and discontinuous finite element schemes in SNIPER to evaluate POS [17].

With increasing computing power, many recent studies employ Monte Carlo (MC) methods. Instead of solving the probability generating function for Pál-Bell equations, the MC method simulates neutron multiplication directly. Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory (LLNL) added POI capability to Mercury [18]. LANL introduced a POI module for MCNP [19]. Booth et al. proved that MC variance-reduction techniques can be applied to POI calculations, which improves computational efficiency [20]. Sjenitzer et al. further enhanced MC simulations using strategies such as forced precursor decay and implicit fission [21]. Durkee showed that mainstream MC codes struggle with SNTE because long neutron chains create heavy computational and memory burdens [22]. To improve robustness, LANL modified MCNP6 to control fission-chain behavior and developed MCATK to compute statistical moments of neutron population and fission rate. Xiao et al. solved the SNTE using a GSMP framework. They developed MES to directly simulate POI, the prompt neutron decay constant (PNDC), and the BWT [23], [24]. Shang added a stochastic transport module in RMC to compute POI, POS, and the BWT [25]. The transition from stochastic evolution to quasi-static methods was also studied to improve efficiency [26].

1.3. Highlights of This Work

This study uses the Monte Carlo particle-transport code NECP-MCX, developed by the Nuclear Engineering Computational Physics (NECP) Laboratory of Xi'an Jiaotong University [27]. NECP-MCX was initially designed to tackle deep-penetration radiation-shielding problems. This work implements an SNTE simulation module in NECP-MCX for weak-source reactor start-up. The code is then applied to supercritical systems to compute the BWT for bare plutonium spheres and the CALIBAN fast burst reactor.

2. METHODS AND CODE DEVELOPMENT

The time-dependent SNTE is solved directly using the MC method. This approach requires high algorithmic efficiency and substantial computing resources. This section first describes the procedure for calculating the BWT in supercritical systems.

2.1. BWT Simulation

Fast burst reactor experiments examine neutron initiation under step reactivity insertion. The system is first placed in a delayed subcritical state and allowed to relax. A burst rod is then inserted rapidly to drive the system prompt supercritical. The interval between rod insertion and the neutron burst reaching a preset level is defined as the BWT.

Because spontaneous fission and delayed precursors continuously generate neutrons, a burst will eventually occur. Figure 1 illustrates the process for simulating a single fission chain using the MC method. System evolution is discretized into small time-steps to control and examine the neutron population. The calculation starts with no initial neutrons. The calculation proceeds as follows:

1. First, initialize the calculation parameters. Within each time-step, transport each alive neutron. Neutron population control is applied when needed.
2. When no neutrons are alive in the current time-step, the algorithm determines the next source-event time. It then samples the corresponding source neutrons and transports them to the boundary of the current time-step.
3. After Step 1 or 2, all source-events within the current time-step are identified. The corresponding source neutrons are sampled and transported.

a. Flow chart of simulating a fission chain to attain BWT. b. Flow chart of finding the next earliest emitted neutron. c. Flow chart of searching for all source-events within the current time-step.

Figure 1. Flow chart of simulating a fission chain with MC method.

The above subroutines are explained in detail in the following sections.

2.2. Control the Neutron Population during Simulating Alive Neutrons

For supercritical systems, even with very small time-steps, the neutrons can increase rapidly. This growth increases memory usage and computational load. Both proposed a weight-conserving importance-weighted comb technique for MC [28]. This technique is used for controlling the neutron population. Let N denote the activation threshold. The comb technique is applied when the total weight of alive neutrons exceeds N . A neutron chain initiated by source neutrons can multiply to K particles, each with unit weight, where $K > N$. The comb technique then resamples these K particles into N particles. The length of the comb is the total neutron weight:

$$W = \sum_{i=1}^K w_i = K \quad (1)$$

The tooth positions are uniformly spaced. This study defines:

$$t_m = \xi \frac{W}{N} + (m-1) \frac{W}{N} \quad m = 1, \dots, N \quad (2)$$

where ξ is a random number between 0 and 1. Each tooth falls into an interval defined by the cumulative weight. The particle in that interval is selected and assigned a new weight:

$$w'_i = \frac{W}{N} = \frac{K}{N} > w_i \quad (3)$$

Thus, K neutrons are resampled into N neutrons. Each selected neutron receives an increased weight.

2.3. Find the Next Emitted Neutron

Figure 1(b) summarizes the procedure used to sample the next source-event time when no neutrons are alive. Only a brief description is provided here. Both spontaneous fission and delayed neutron emission can be modeled as Poisson processes, and the probability of observing n source-events in time t is:

$$P(N(t) = n) = \frac{(\lambda t)^n e^{-\lambda t}}{n!} \quad (4)$$

where λ is the source-event occurrence rate. It applies to both delayed precursor decay and spontaneous fission. This equation gives the probability that n source-events occur within time t . Therefore, the interval between source-events follows an exponential distribution:

$$P(X > t) = P(N(t) = 0) = e^{-\lambda t} \quad (5)$$

where t is the interval between two source-events. It represents the probability that no source-events occur during $[0, t]$. The emission time is sampled by:

$$t = -\frac{1}{\lambda} \ln \xi \quad (6)$$

For spontaneous fission sources, the number of emitted neutrons is not taken as the Evaluated Nuclear Data File (ENDF) average value alone. Instead, it is sampled from the fission multiplicity distribution defined by:

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\nu} P_n = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\nu - \bar{\nu} + \frac{1}{2} - b} \frac{1}{\sigma} e^{-\frac{t^2}{2}} dt \quad (7)$$

Equation (7) defines the cumulative distribution function (CDF) for the emitted-neutron multiplicity. Here, P_n is the probability of producing n neutrons, $\bar{\nu}$ is the average neutron yield per fission event, σ is the root-mean-square width of the Gaussian distribution and is typically set to 1.08, and b is a small correction factor. The treatment of induced fission is similar to that for spontaneous fission.

2.4. Searching for All Source-Events at the Current Time-step

Figure 1(c) shows the procedure for processing all source-events in the current time-step. Compared with spontaneous fission sources, delayed precursors require a more complex treatment. This is because fission induced by delayed neutrons produces new delayed precursors during the current time-step. A precursor is taken from the precursor bank and checked for emission within the current time-step. If it emits, the corresponding delayed neutron is sampled and transported immediately. Otherwise, the precursor is moved to a temporary bank for the next time-step. Any newly generated precursors are inserted into the current precursor bank, so all precursors are eventually processed. After transporting all delayed neutrons within the current time-step, the data from the temporary bank is moved to the precursor bank for next time-step.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

Two benchmark sets were selected to verify the NECP-MCX capability for SNTE calculations. The first set is deeply prompt supercritical (bare plutonium spheres). The second set is slightly prompt supercritical (CALIBAN).

3.1. Benchmarks for Bare Plutonium Spheres

LLNL proposed a set of benchmarks for high-enrichment bare plutonium spheres [18], and their geometric parameters are listed in Table I. The atomic fractions are as follows: Ga is 2.6030×10^{-2} , ^{239}Pu is 9.1305×10^{-1} , ^{240}Pu is 5.6440×10^{-2} , and ^{241}Pu is 4.48×10^{-3} . According to Ref. [24], the strength of spontaneous fission is 3.6665×10^5 fissions/s.

The k_{eff} values were calculated. Except for case 100, which is critical, all other cases are deeply prompt supercritical. Therefore, case 100 could not be ignited by source neutrons. For each case, 1,000 fission

chains were performed, and the neutron population was examined every 1 ns. The divergence criterion was set to 10,000. Table II compares BWTs, showing that NECP-MCX agrees well with 0-D MC [24] and RMC [25].

Table I. Geometric parameters of bare plutonium spheres.

Density · Radius ($\text{g} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$)	Density ($\text{g} \cdot \text{cm}^{-3}$)	Radius (cm)
100	15.7	6.3694
120	20.6	5.8252
140	26.0	5.3846
160	31.8	5.0314
180	37.9	4.7493

Table II. Results of bare plutonium spheres.

Density · Radius ($\text{g} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$)	k_{eff} (1)	Waiting time & Standard deviation (μs) 0-D MC [24]	Waiting time & Standard deviation (μs) RMC [25]	Waiting time & Standard deviation (μs) NECP-MCX
100	1.0007			
120	1.1654	14.2/13.2	14.6/14.6	13.97/13.82
140	1.3177	8.74/8.49	8.7/8.8	8.61/8.47
160	1.4564	6.46/6.28	6.4/7.1	6.45/6.18
180	1.5827	5.50/5.36	5.8/6.5	5.44/5.59

3.2. CALIBAN Benchmark

The CALIBAN burst reactor was constructed by CEA to study weak-source start-up [29]. It uses 93.5% enriched U–Mo fuel (113 kg) in two parts, with a fixed upper section and movable lower section. The core has a 195 mm outer diameter and a 30 mm central channel. Control and excursion rods are made of the same U–Mo alloy with 0.1 mm nickel cladding. For CALIBAN, the delayed neutron fraction is 0.00659 and the prompt neutron lifetime is 10 ns.

Ratel summarized data [30] from 114 burst experiments conducted under the weak-source conditions of Caliban reactor [29]. The experimental conditions were:

1. The prompt supercritical reactivity at the burst was $1.083 \beta_{\text{eff}}$, with a standard deviation of $0.002 \beta_{\text{eff}}$.
2. The reactor shutdown time before the burst was 15 min, and $k_{\text{eff}} = 0.9$;
3. After the core was assembled, it reached the delayed supercritical point (approximately 60 s, $k_{\text{eff}} = 1.00129$). After waiting for approximately 11 seconds, the excursion rod was inserted rapidly (75 mm travel, 250 ms). This insertion added a reactivity of $0.888 \beta_{\text{eff}}$. The system then became prompt supercritical with $1.083 \beta_{\text{eff}}$ ($k_{\text{eff}} = 1.00719$).
4. The burst was generated, and the time required for the system power to reach 1 kW was recorded.

With the top of the excursion rod set at 74 mm, the k_{eff} calculated by NECP-MCX was 1.00728. According to the literature, at this moment, the system had undergone a long period of precursor accumulation, and the intrinsic source strength had increased from 118.3 n/s (spontaneous fission) to 1184 n/s in total [29]. In the present NECP-MCX implementation, geometry variation during rod motion is not modeled. Therefore, the calculations start from the maximum reactivity state at $\rho = 1.083 \beta_{\text{eff}}$. The equilibrium delayed neutron spectra for ^{235}U fission were obtained from the literature [31]. The calculation time-step was set to 0.01 s. The fission rate at the burst was not explicitly given. Therefore, results for different prescribed fission rates are shown in Figure 2. The BWT of CALIBAN gradually converges as the cutoff fission rate increases. This is because, once the fission rate enters an exponential-growth regime, the burst is triggered within a very short time.

Table III lists the BWT results with a cutoff fission rate of 5×10^8 . It also includes the experimental results and the calculated results from the 0-D MC code [29] and RMC [25]. The BWT induced by a Poisson source follows a gamma distribution. Figure 3 shows the 256 NECP-MCX samples and the fitted gamma curves. The NECP-MCX results show closer agreement with the 3-D MC results from RMC than with the experimental measurements. The error between NECP-MCX and experiments is largely attributable to the approximate treatment of precursor accumulation and decay during the earlier delayed supercritical stage.

Figure 2. The BWT of CALIBAN varies with the cutoff fission rate.

Table III. Results of CALIBAN.

<i>Method</i>	Waiting time & Standard deviation (s)
Experiments	0.742/0.7
0-D MC	0.808/0.75
RMC (3-D MC)	0.680/0.53
NECP-MCX (3-D MC)	0.706/0.53

Figure 3. Probability density (after normalization) and gamma fit of CALIBAN BWT from simulation of NECP-MCX.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

A stochastic dynamics MC capability for computing the BWT of prompt supercritical systems has been developed in NECP-MCX. By explicitly handling delayed precursors and solving time-dependent SNTE, benchmarks such as bare plutonium spheres and CALIBAN were successfully simulated. The calculated results agree well with other 3-D MC codes and reproduce the experimental mean waiting-time with reasonable accuracy. The error between NECP-MCX and experiments in the distribution shape is mainly attributable to the simplified treatment of precursor history during the delayed

supercritical stage. Future work will focus on extending the MC treatment to account for geometric motion, with the aim of more accurately predicting the distribution of BWT.

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